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EMPOWERING EVERY USER: WEB ACCESSIBILITY AND ACCESSIBLE LIBRARY SERVICES IN ACCORDANCE WITH RANGANATHAN'S SECOND LAW

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the intersection of web accessibility and library services through the lens of Ranganathan's Second Law, "Every reader his/her book." In today's digital era, where online platforms serve as primary sources of information, ensuring equitable access to library resources for all users, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, is imperative. The paper begins by elucidating Ranganathan's Five Laws of Library Science, focusing specifically on the Second Law's emphasis on personalized service and resource allocation. It then delves into the significance of web accessibility standards in fulfilling the mission of libraries to provide every user with their "book" or information resource. Through a comprehensive literature review, the paper examines various studies addressing web accessibility challenges faced by library users, including those with disabilities, and proposes solutions and best practices for addressing these challenges. By correlating Ranganathan's Second Law with the principles of web accessibility, the paper highlights the importance of inclusive design practices and user-centered approaches in creating accessible library services. Ultimately, the paper advocates for the integration of web accessibility standards into library services to empower every user and advance the mission of libraries in promoting inclusivity and equal access to knowledge in the digital age.

Keywords: *Web Accessibility, Library Services, Ranganathan's Second Law, Every Reader his/her Book, Inclusivity, Digital Age*

1. Introduction

In the realm of library science, S. R. Ranganathan's Five Laws stand as foundational principles guiding the organization and operation of libraries worldwide. These laws encapsulate the core values and objectives of the profession, shaping the way librarians curate, disseminate, and manage information resources (Sen, 2008). At the heart of Ranganathan's laws lies a profound commitment to inclusivity and accessibility, with each law illuminating a facet of this overarching ethos (Leiter, 2003). Following Ranganathan's Five Laws, embark a journey through the fundamental tenets that underpin the mission of libraries (Ranganathan, 1931):

- **Books are for Use:** Emphasizes libraries' role in facilitating information access.
- **Every Reader his/her Book:** Stresses equitable access for all users.
- **Every Book its Reader:** Highlights the importance of connecting users with relevant resources.
- **Save the Time of the Reader:** Advocates for efficient information retrieval.
- **The Library is a Growing Organism:** Encourages adaptation and innovation.

At the core of this paper lies Ranganathan's Second Law, "Every reader his/her book," advocating for equitable access to information in libraries, regardless of users' backgrounds or abilities, fostering diversity and personalized service (Bhatt, 2011). This principle prompts efficient resource allocation and tailored services to empower patrons, aligning with the paper's exploration of leveraging web accessibility and accessible library services in ensuring universal access to information in the digital age. In today's digital landscape, where online platforms dominate information access, prioritizing web accessibility standards becomes imperative for libraries. Ensuring digital content and interfaces are perceivable, operable, understandable and robust for all users (BOIA, 2019), including those with disabilities, breaks down barriers to information access (Nazim et al., 2021). By embracing accessible design principles and technologies, libraries uphold inclusivity and equality, embodying Ranganathan's Second Law by providing every user with their "book" or information resource, irrespective of the medium of access.

2. Literature Review

The literature review encompassed ten studies addressing various aspects of web accessibility and library services, with each offering valuable insights into the challenges faced by library users, particularly those with disabilities. While these studies may not directly address the specific theme of the present study, they collectively emphasize the significance of accessibility for library resources. **Getts and Stewart (2018)** identified a gap in literature concerning distance library services for deaf and hard of hearing (D/HH) users, underscoring the need for targeted strategies tailored to this community. **Anyim (2020)** investigated the accessibility and utilization of web resources by college students, revealing challenges such as poor internet connectivity and inadequate ICT infrastructure. **Brunskill (2020)** interviewed university students with disabilities about their preferences for library website accessibility features, highlighting the importance of user feedback in design. **Agyeiku (2021)** evaluated the accessibility and use of library resources in a university setting, emphasizing the need for comprehensive information literacy training. **Annabathuni et al. (2021)** examined the availability and accessibility of library information resources, addressing challenges such as information overload. **Mubofu and Malekani (2021)** explored the accessibility of library resources for distance learners, revealing challenges such as high data costs. Singh (2021)

examined accessibility measures in law university libraries, highlighting the need for additional assistive technologies. **Ezell et al. (2022)** provided an overview of current accessibility efforts in academic libraries, emphasizing variations in accessibility features on library websites. **Pope and Creed-Dikeogu (2022)** focused on improving the accessibility of library video tutorials, emphasizing the importance of features such as closed captioning. **Tiurkedzhy et al. (2022)** evaluated the current state of library web content accessibility, highlighting shortcomings in compliance with accessibility standards. Overall, the literature emphasizes the significance of targeted approaches and user-centered design practices in improving accessibility within library environments.

3. Study Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

- i) To understand the basic concept of web accessibility and accessibility guidelines.
- ii) To explore the concept of accessible library services and their role in promoting inclusivity.
- iii) To investigate the role of libraries in promoting inclusivity and accommodating diverse user needs.
- iv) To examine the correlation between Ranganathan's Second Law and web accessibility principles.
- v) To identify challenges faced in implementing web accessibility in library services and propose solutions.
- vi) To explore potential future directions for further enhancing inclusivity and accessibility in library environments.

4. Understanding Web Accessibility

The Web is designed fundamentally to perform for all people, irrespective of their hardware, software, language, place, or skill. When the Web achieves this goal, it is accessible to people with a diverse range of hearing, movement, sight and cognitive abilities. Thus, the impact of disability is radically changed on the Web because the Web removes barriers to communication and interaction that many people face in the physical world. However, when websites, applications, technologies, or tools are poorly designed, these can create barriers that exclude people from using the Web. It is important that the Web be accessible to ensure equal access and equal opportunities for people with different skills. Web accessibility depends on several components acting together, including Web technologies, Web browsers and other user agents, authoring tools, and websites (W3C_WAI, 2019).

4.1. Accessibility Guidelines

Accessibility Guidelines Working Group of W3C developed a series of interrelated accessibility guidelines that include the Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG), the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) and the User Agent Accessibility Guidelines (UAAG). Essential components of Web Accessibility have relationships between these different guidelines.

Figure 1. Relations between the components of web accessibility

- i) **Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG)** - ATAG provides instructions for making authoring tools accessible, enabling persons with disabilities to create web content. They promote the production of WCAG-compliant content by supporting authors, including web developers and designers, who use authoring tools for creating various types of web content such as static web pages and dynamic web applications (W3C_WAI, 2020). Targeting Web-based CMS, courseware tools, and content aggregators, ATAG is intended for policymakers, managers, and others. Developed by the W3C WAI Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines Working Group (ATAG WG), ATAG 1.0 was certified in February 2000 and ATAG 2.0 in September 2015 (W3C_WAI, 2015a).
- ii) **User Agent Accessibility Guidelines (UAAG)** - UAAG discusses enhancing user agent accessibility for people with disabilities, encompassing browsers, extensions, media players, and other web-rendering apps. Developed by the User Agent Accessibility Guidelines Working Group (UAWG) under W3C_WAI (W3C_WAI, 2016), UAAG 1.0 was certified in December 2002, and UAAG 2.0 in December 2015 (W3C_WAI, 2015b). UAAG 2.0 user agents improve accessibility through their user interface and compatibility with assistive technologies, benefiting all users, not just those with disabilities.
- iii) **Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)** - The WCAG standards aim to continuously improve web accessibility for individuals with disabilities, evolving alongside advancements in technology and design. Developed by the W3C Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) in collaboration with stakeholders worldwide, WCAG serves as a comprehensive standard essential for meeting the diverse needs of individuals, businesses, and governments globally. These guidelines offer crucial guidance for ensuring web content accessibility, validated through both automated and human reviews (BOIA, 2019). Initially published in 1999 as WCAG 1.0 (W3C_WAI, 1998), subsequent evaluations have led to updates over time. The latest stable version, WCAG 2.2, was published on May 21, 2021 (W3C, 2021), while WCAG 3.0 is currently in progress, with the latest working draft released on July 24, 2023 (W3C, 2023).

5. Accessible Library Services

Accessible library services refer to the provision of library resources, facilities, and programs in a manner that ensures equitable access for all users, including those with disabilities or other special needs. These services aim to remove barriers to information access and promote

inclusivity within library environments. Accessible library services encompass a range of initiatives, such as:

- **Physical Accessibility:** Ensuring that library buildings, entrances, aisles, and facilities are designed to accommodate users with mobility impairments, including wheelchair ramps, accessible restrooms, and designated parking spaces.
- **Digital Accessibility:** Making library websites, catalogs, and online resources accessible to users with visual, auditory, or motor impairments through features such as alternative text for images, keyboard navigation, and screen reader compatibility.
- **Assistive Technologies:** Providing assistive devices and technologies, such as screen readers, magnifiers, Braille displays, and hearing loops, to enhance access to library materials and services for users with disabilities.
- **Accessible Formats:** Offering library materials in alternative formats, such as large print, audio, or digital text, to accommodate users with print disabilities or other reading challenges.
- **Library Programming:** Designing inclusive programs, workshops, and events that cater to the diverse needs and interests of all library users, including individuals with disabilities, seniors, and non-native language speakers.
- **Staff Training and Awareness:** Providing training for library staff on disability awareness, inclusive communication, and assistive technology usage to better support users with disabilities and provide equitable service.
- **Policy and Advocacy:** Developing library policies and advocating for resources and funding to support the ongoing improvement of accessible library services, as well as promoting awareness of accessibility issues within the broader community.

By implementing accessible library services, libraries can foster an environment where all individuals, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, can fully participate in and benefit from the wealth of resources and opportunities offered by the library.

6. Role of Libraries in Promoting Inclusivity and Accommodating Diverse User Needs

Libraries play a crucial role in promoting inclusivity and accommodating diverse user needs in several ways:

- **Equal Access to Information:** Libraries strive to provide equitable access to information for all individuals, regardless of their backgrounds, abilities, or socio-economic status. By offering a wide range of resources in various formats, libraries ensure that everyone has the opportunity to explore and engage with information that meets their unique needs and interests.
- **Tailored Services:** Libraries recognize that each user may have different preferences and requirements when accessing information. As such, they offer personalized services and

assistance to help users navigate their collections, access digital resources, and find the materials they need.

- **Accessibility Initiatives:** Libraries implement accessibility initiatives to remove barriers to access for users with disabilities. This includes providing accessible facilities, assistive technologies, and alternative formats for materials to ensure that everyone can fully participate in library services.
- **Inclusive Programming:** Libraries develop inclusive programming and events that cater to diverse user interests and needs. This may include workshops, classes, and cultural events that celebrate different communities and perspectives, fostering a sense of belonging and community engagement.
- **Education and Advocacy:** Libraries educate their communities about the importance of inclusivity and diversity, promoting awareness and understanding of different cultures, identities, and abilities. They also advocate for policies and resources that support inclusivity and diversity within the library and the wider community.

Overall, libraries serve as vital hubs for promoting inclusivity and accommodating diverse user needs by providing equal access to information, personalized services, accessible facilities, inclusive programming, and educational initiatives. Through their efforts, libraries create welcoming and supportive environments where everyone can thrive and access the resources they need to succeed.

7. Correlating Ranganathan's Second Law with Web Accessibility

Understanding the profound resonance between Ranganathan's Second Law and the principles of web accessibility, delving into the essence of inclusivity emerges as paramount. Analyze how Ranganathan's Second Law, with its emphatic proclamation of "Every reader his/her book," finds a harmonious echo in the ethos of web accessibility. Here, the emphasis is not merely on providing access to information, but on ensuring that this access is unimpeded, unrestricted, and equitable for all individuals, regardless of their abilities or disabilities. The following table provides some areas and parameters in which Ranganathan's Second Law correlates with Web Accessibility.

Table 1: Correlation Between Ranganathan's Second Law and Web Accessibility

Sr. No.	Ranganathan's Second Law: "Every Reader his/her Book"	Web Accessibility
1	Equitable Access: Advocates for ensuring that all individuals have equal opportunities to access information resources, regardless of their physical or cognitive abilities, socio-economic status, or other characteristics.	Equitable Access to Digital Content: Ensures that digital content and services are accessible to all users, including those with disabilities, by adhering to accessibility standards and guidelines such as WCAG.
2	Personalized Service: Highlights the importance of tailoring library services to meet the diverse needs and preferences of individual users, ensuring that each person receives assistance and resources	Accessible Design and Content: Promotes the creation of digital interfaces and content that are perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust for users with diverse abilities and needs.

	suited to their unique requirements.	
3	Unique Information Needs: Recognizes that users have varied information-seeking behaviors, preferences, and requirements, emphasizing the importance of offering a diverse range of resources and services to accommodate these differences.	Personalization and Customization: Supports the provision of options for users to personalize their digital experiences, such as adjusting text size or color contrast, to better accommodate their preferences and requirements.
4	Inclusivity and Diversity: Promotes an inclusive and diverse environment within libraries, where all users are welcomed and provided with equal opportunities to engage with information resources, regardless of their backgrounds or identities.	Inclusive Digital Environments: Advocates for the development of digital environments that are inclusive and welcoming to all users, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, fostering a sense of belonging and empowerment.
5	Accommodating User Preferences and Abilities: Stresses the significance of designing library services and resources in a way that accommodates users' preferences, abilities, and limitations, ensuring that everyone can navigate and utilize library facilities effectively.	Barrier-Free Information Access: Strives to eliminate barriers to accessing digital information, ensuring that all users can navigate, interact with, and understand digital content and services effectively, irrespective of their individual characteristics or limitations.

By aligning Ranganathan's Second Law with the principles of web accessibility, libraries and digital content creators can work towards creating inclusive environments where every user can find their "book" or information resource, irrespective of their individual characteristics or needs.

8. Challenges and Solutions

Implementing web accessibility in library services can pose several challenges, including:

- **Limited Resources:** Libraries often operate with limited budgets and staffing, making it challenging to allocate resources for web accessibility initiatives. This can hinder the implementation of necessary changes to websites and digital platforms to ensure accessibility for all users.
- **Technical Complexity:** Web accessibility standards and guidelines can be complex and technical, requiring specialized knowledge and expertise to implement effectively. Libraries may lack the necessary technical skills or training among staff to address accessibility issues on their websites and digital resources.
- **Legacy Systems and Content:** Libraries may have existing websites and digital content that were created using outdated technologies or design practices, making them inaccessible to users with disabilities. Updating or retrofitting these legacy systems to meet modern accessibility standards can be time-consuming and resource-intensive.
- **Content Management Challenges:** Libraries often manage large volumes of digital content, including text, images, videos, and interactive elements. Ensuring the

accessibility of this content across various platforms and devices can be challenging, particularly when content is created or managed by multiple contributors.

- **Lack of Awareness and Training:** There may be a lack of awareness among library staff about the importance of web accessibility and how to implement it effectively. Training and education initiatives are essential to raise awareness and build capacity among staff to address accessibility issues in library services.
- **Legal and Compliance Obligations:** Libraries are subject to legal and regulatory requirements related to web accessibility, including compliance with standards such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG). Meeting these obligations can be complex and may require ongoing monitoring and updates to ensure compliance.
- **User Engagement and Feedback:** Engaging users with disabilities in the accessibility design and testing process is essential for identifying barriers and ensuring that digital resources meet their needs. However, libraries may face challenges in soliciting meaningful feedback and engaging users with diverse disabilities in the accessibility evaluation process.

Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort from library leadership, staff, and stakeholders to prioritize web accessibility, allocate resources effectively, build technical expertise, raise awareness, and engage users in the design and testing of accessible digital services. Below are some best practices for tackling these challenges:

- **Allocate Resources Appropriately:** Prioritize web accessibility in budgeting and resource allocation, ensuring that sufficient funds and staff time are dedicated to accessibility initiatives. Consider leveraging external resources, such as grants or partnerships with accessibility experts, to supplement internal efforts.
- **Training and Capacity Building:** Provide ongoing training and professional development opportunities for library staff to enhance their knowledge and skills in web accessibility. Offer workshops, online courses, and access to resources such as accessibility guidelines and toolkits to support staff in implementing accessible design practices.
- **Adopt Accessible Design Principles:** Incorporate accessible design principles into the development and maintenance of library websites and digital platforms. Follow established guidelines such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) to ensure that digital content is perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust for users with disabilities.
- **Regular Accessibility Audits:** Conduct regular accessibility audits of library websites and digital resources to identify and address accessibility barriers. Use automated testing tools, manual evaluations, and user testing with individuals with disabilities to ensure that digital content meets accessibility standards and user needs.
- **Engage Users with Disabilities:** Involve users with disabilities in the design, development, and testing of library websites and digital services. Solicit feedback,

conduct usability testing, and prioritize the needs and preferences of users with diverse disabilities to ensure that digital resources are accessible and usable for all.

- **Collaborate with Accessibility Experts:** Collaborate with accessibility experts, consultants, or organizations with expertise in web accessibility to provide guidance, support, and technical assistance in implementing accessibility best practices. Seek out partnerships and resources within the accessibility community to leverage knowledge and expertise.
- **Promote Accessibility Awareness:** Raise awareness about the importance of web accessibility among library staff, stakeholders, and the broader community. Offer educational programs, presentations, and outreach initiatives to increase understanding of accessibility issues and promote a culture of inclusion within the library.

9. Future Directions

Here are some potential future developments and opportunities for further enhancing inclusivity and accessibility in library environments:

- **Advancements in Assistive Technologies:** With rapid advancements in technology, there is an opportunity to leverage emerging assistive technologies to enhance accessibility in libraries. This includes innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI), natural language processing (NLP), and machine learning (ML) algorithms to develop more sophisticated assistive tools and services for users with disabilities.
- **Virtual and Augmented Reality:** Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) technologies offer new possibilities for creating immersive and interactive library experiences that are accessible to users with disabilities. Libraries can explore the integration of VR/AR tools to provide alternative ways for users to access information and engage with library resources.
- **Universal Design Principles:** Embracing universal design principles in library architecture, technology, and services can further enhance inclusivity by ensuring that library environments are accessible to users of all ages, abilities, and backgrounds. This involves designing spaces, interfaces, and resources that are flexible, adaptable, and intuitive for diverse user needs.
- **Collaborative Partnerships:** Libraries can strengthen their efforts to promote inclusivity and accessibility by forging collaborative partnerships with disability advocacy organizations, educational institutions, government agencies, and technology companies. These partnerships can facilitate knowledge sharing, resource sharing, and joint initiatives to address accessibility challenges and promote best practices.
- **Community Engagement and Co-Creation:** Engaging users with disabilities as active partners in the design, development, and evaluation of library services and resources can lead to more inclusive and user-centered solutions. Libraries can create opportunities for co-creation and co-design through user advisory groups, focus groups, and participatory design workshops.

- **Data-driven Decision Making:** Leveraging data analytics and user feedback mechanisms can provide insights into user behavior, preferences, and accessibility needs, enabling libraries to make informed decisions about resource allocation, service improvements, and accessibility enhancements.
- **Policy Advocacy and Leadership:** Libraries can play a proactive role in advocating for policies, legislation, and funding initiatives that support accessibility and inclusivity in library environments. By demonstrating leadership in accessibility initiatives and serving as advocates for change, libraries can contribute to creating more equitable and accessible communities.

By embracing these future developments and opportunities, libraries can continue to advance their efforts to promote inclusivity and accessibility, ensuring that all users have equal opportunities to access and benefit from library resources and services.

10. Conclusion

The intersection of Ranganathan's Second Law with the principles of web accessibility underscores the fundamental commitment of libraries to inclusivity and equitable access to information. By aligning with the ethos of "Every reader his/her book," libraries strive to create environments where all individuals, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, can access and engage with information resources effectively. While challenges exist in implementing web accessibility in library services, various solutions and best practices offer pathways for progress. Looking ahead, the future holds promising opportunities for further enhancing inclusivity and accessibility in library environments through advancements in technology, collaborative partnerships, and community engagement. By continuing to prioritize accessibility initiatives, libraries can play a pivotal role in fostering a more inclusive society where everyone has the opportunity to participate fully in the digital age.

References

- Agyeiku, J. (2021). Accessibility and Use of Library Resources in the North Campus Library of the University of Education, Winneba. *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-Journal)*, 1–33. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6491>
- Annabathuni, R. K., Pitla, R. S. K., & Naick, B. R. D. (2021). Accessibility of Library Resources at KIET Group of Institutions, Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-Journal)*, 1–21. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5983/>
- Anyim, W. O. (2020). Accessibility and Utilisation of Web Resources by Students in FCT College of Education Zuba, Abuja. *Electronic Research Journal of Engineering, Computer and Applied Sciences*, 2, 78–91. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345495334>
- Bhatt, R. (2011). Relevance of Ranganathan's Laws of Library Science in Library Marketing. *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-Journal)*, 1–8. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/551>

- Brunskill, A. (2020). "Without That Detail, I'm Not Coming": The Perspectives of Students with Disabilities on Accessibility Information Provided on Academic Library Websites. *College & Research Libraries*, 81(5), 768. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.5.768>
- Bureau of Internet Accessibility (BOIA). (2019, September 13). *What Are the Four Major Categories of Accessibility?* <https://www.boia.org/blog/what-are-the-four-major-categories-of-accessibility>
- Ezell, J., Pionke, J. J., & Gunnoe, J. (2022). Accessible services in academic libraries: a content analysis of library accessibility webpages in the United States. *Reference Services Review*, 50(2), 222–236. <https://doi.org/10.1108/rsr-10-2021-0055>
- Getts, E., & Stewart, K. (2018). Accessibility of distance library services for deaf and hard of hearing users. *Reference Services Review*, 46(3), 439–448. <https://doi.org/10.1108/rsr-03-2018-0032>
- Leiter, R. A. (2003). Reflections on Ranganathan's five laws of library science. *Law Library Journal*, 93(3), 411–418.
- Mubofu, C., & Malekani, A. (2021). Accessibility of Library Resources and Support Services by Distance Learners. *Journal of Library & Information Services in Distance Learning*, 15(4), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533290x.2021.2021345>
- Nazim, M., Beg, A., & Sarkar, M. (2021). Access to library facilities and services for users with disabilities: a study of Aligarh Muslim University in India. *Journal of Access Services*, 18(1), 30–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15367967.2020.1870120>
- Pope, B. M., & Creed-Dikeogu, G. F. (2022). Increasing Accessibility to Academic Library Services with Alt Text, Color Contrast, Captioning, and Transcripts in YouTube Tutorials. *Kansas Library Association College and University Libraries Section Proceedings*, 12(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4148/2160-942x.1085>
- Ranganathan, S. R. (1931). *The five Laws of library science*. Madras Library Association .
- Sen, B. K. (2008). Ranganathan's five laws. *Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS)*, 55(2), 87–90. <http://nopr.niscpr.res.in/handle/123456789/1769>
- Singh, A. (2021). Accessibility of Library Services for Persons with Disabilities: A Study of Services provided by Select Law University Libraries in India. *Indian Journal of Information, Library & Society*, 34(3-4), 189–199.
- Tiurkedzhy, N. S., Davydova, I. O., Marina, O. YU., & Marin, S. O. (2022). Accessibility Analysis of Digital Libraries and Specialized Library Resources. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development*, 7, 218–231. https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2022_270121
- W3C. (2021, May 21). *Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2*. <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG22/>

- W3C. (2023, July 24). *W3C Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 3.0: W3C Working Draft* (J. Spellman, R. B. Montgomery, S. Lauriat, & M. Cooper, Eds.). <https://www.w3.org/TR/wcag-3.0/>
- W3C_WAI. (1998, January 20). *Master Document - Unified Web Accessibility Guidelines* (G. C. Vanderheiden & W. A. Chisholm, Eds.). <https://www.w3.org/WAI/GL/central.htm>
- W3C_WAI. (2015a). *Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG) 2.0*. <https://www.w3.org/TR/ATAG20/>
- W3C_WAI. (2015b). *User Agent Accessibility Guidelines (UAAG) 2.0*. <https://www.w3.org/TR/UAAG20/>
- W3C_WAI. (2016). *User Agent Accessibility Guidelines (UAAG) Overview*. <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/uaag/>
- W3C_WAI. (2019). *Making the Web Accessible: Strategies, standards, and supporting resources to help you make the Web more accessible to people with disabilities*. Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>
- W3C_WAI. (2020, July 1). *Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG) Overview* (S. L. Henry, Ed.). <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/atag/>

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